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Numerical simulation on settlement characteristics and treatment of pavement structure on soft foundation

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Abstract: When building a highway on a soft soil foundation, problems such as excessive settlement and uneven settlement will be encountered, which will directly affect the flatness of the pavement, horizontal drainage, and driving comfort, increase the stress of the pavement structure layer, and lead to early damage of the pavement. Based on the soil consolidation theory, the settlement of four different pavement structures on soft soil foundation is simulated by the finite element method, and the influence of geogrid and CFG pile treatment on the settlement characteristics is studied. The research shows that the four different pavement structures with the same thickness have similar long-term settlement, the initial settlement is faster, and the following settlement speed is slower. Fifteen years after completion, the differential settlement of the pavement surface reaches 1.4 cm. Increasing the elastic modulus of the subbase has little effect on the settlement. The thickness of the base course should be controlled within a reasonable range, and the thickness of the appropriate graded gravel layer should be controlled within 12 to 18 cm. The simulation of ground reinforcement indicates that using a geogrid alone has minimal effect on reducing settlement in soft soil foundations. However, after adding CFG pile groups, the settlement at completion and after 15 years is significantly reduced, with minimal differential settlement, effectively controlling uneven subsidence of the subgrade. Sensitivity analysis shows that the factors influencing settlement, in descending order of impact, are pile length, pavement thickness, base layer modulus, and geogrid spacing. The length of the CFG piles is the key factor controlling settlement. When the pile length increases from 8 m to 15 m, the pavement settlement decreases from 9.8 cm to 1.4 cm, a reduction of 85.7%. The combined solution of geogrid + CFG piles has the lowest life-cycle cost.

1. Introduction

Due to the characteristics of soft soil, such as high-water content, high compressibility, low permeability, low strength, and a thick soil layer, problems such as excessive settlement and uneven settlement will be encountered when building a highway on soft soil foundation^[1]. Under the action of traffic load, the pavement is prone to lateral slip and creep, which has a great impact on the subgrade and structures. Uneven settlement refers to the difference in the lateral or longitudinal settlement of the pavement structure caused by different soft soil properties or soft foundation treatment. The uneven settlement in this paper is the difference in the settlement between the shoulder and the midpoint of the pavement in the lateral direction of the pavement. On the one hand, this uneven settlement will affect the flatness of the pavement, the lateral drainage of the pavement, and the comfort of driving. On the other hand, it will cause additional stress in the pavement structure layer. After superposition with the load stress caused by the driving load, it may exceed the ultimate strength of the pavement structural materials, leading to early damage of the pavement^{[2][3]}. Therefore, it is necessary to develop a suitable pavement structure

in soft soil areas and obtain the optimal treatment scheme to solve the settlement problem. It is of great significance to improve the service level of pavement and extend the service life of pavement.

The settlement problem has always been one of the main research topics in soil mechanics. Since Terzaghi established the consolidation theory in 1923, the relevant calculation theory of foundation settlement has been greatly developed. At present, there are three main types of analysis and calculation methods for foundation settlement. The first type is the theoretical formula method based on elastic theory and Terzaghi consolidation theory, but this method does not consider the nonlinear deformation and lateral deformation of soil mass, and has certain limitations^{[4][5]}. The second type is the settlement prediction method, that is, in engineering application, the settlement of each structure is measured by precision instruments at different times, and the relationship between settlement and time is obtained to predict the settlement, such as hyperbolic method and gray prediction method, but this method has a large workload and needs to be based on accurate and effective measured data^{[6][7]}. The third type is the finite element numerical analysis method. Based on Biot consolidation theory and the nonlinear and elastoplastic constitutive model of soil materials, a finite element model of subgrade settlement is established to calculate the stress and displacement at each model element at any time^{[8][9][10]}. The finite element method can reflect the lateral deformation of the model and the nonlinear deformation of the soil; the complex boundary conditions are also considered. At present, it has been widely used in the analysis of soil foundation settlement^{[11][12]}.

The high compressibility and low permeability of soft soil foundation can easily lead to excessive settlement of the road surface. In this paper, the Drucker-Prager (D-P) elastoplastic model is used to establish the numerical model of highway soft soil subgrade structure. The settlement of different pavement structures is simulated by the finite element method, the effects of geogrid and CFG pile reinforcement on the settlement characteristics are studied, and the sensitivity of the main parameters affecting the settlement is analyzed.

2. Theory of soil settlement

As early as the beginning of the 20th century, Terzaghi established the classic foundation settlement analysis method. The settlement is divided into three parts according to its deformation: initial settlement, consolidation settlement, and secondary consolidation settlement. The consolidation of soil includes the seepage of water and the deformation of soil, which is a coupling problem between them^{[13][14]}. The two-dimensional equation based on Biot's consolidation theory is:

$$\text{Equilibrium differential equation: } \frac{\partial \sigma_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \sigma_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \gamma = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{Continuity equation: } \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) - \frac{1}{\gamma_w} \left(\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} k_x + \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial y^2} k_y \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

where x and y are coordinate directions, σ and τ are effective stress, p is pore water stress, γ is saturated unit weight of soil mass, γ_w is unit weight of water, and k_x and k_y are soil permeability coefficient in x and y direction respectively.

Equations (1), (2), and (3) include three unknown variables: displacement u and v , and pore pressure p . The displacement and stress changes at each point of the soil can be obtained by solving the equations simultaneously.

3. Calculation model and parameters

3.1. Pavement structure model

The cross section width of the subgrade is 60 m, the top width of the embankment pavement is 28 m, the filling height is 4 m, and the embankment slope is 1:1.5. The geological survey shows that the soft soil in this area is muddy clay and silty clay from the surface to the bottom, and the groundwater level is 1.0 m below the ground. The thickness of muddy clay in soft soil foundation is 11.5 m, and the

thickness of silty clay is 8.0 m. The two sides of the foundation are assumed to be frictionless x-direction constraints, and the bottom of the foundation is assumed to be frictionless x and y-direction constraints. The bottom and both sides of the foundation are impermeable boundaries, and the surface and the top of the embankment are impermeable boundaries. The thickness of the sand cushion is 0.5 m, and the groundwater level is 1.0 m below the surface of the sand cushion. The foundation and embankment are analyzed as plane strain problems. The numerical analysis method in this paper uses quadrilateral elements to divide the grid, with a node spacing of about 1.0 m. There are 1, 534 elements and 1, 621 nodes in total. The pavement structure calculation model is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Calculation model of pavement structure.

3.2. Pavement structure

When building a highway on a soft soil foundation, it is necessary to focus on the adverse effects of uneven settlement of the foundation on the pavement structure. When designing the pavement structure, these should be considered: (1) A thick asphalt surface layer is used to reduce the effect of traffic load on the soft foundation and relieve uneven settlement; (2) The graded crushed stone interlayer structure is adopted to give full play to the ability of graded crushed to coordinate deformation and the ability of cement stabilized crushed under the graded crushed layer to mitigate uneven settlement.

In this paper, four pavement structures and a conventional semi-rigid base asphalt pavement are designed. The thickness of four pavement structures is 69-78 cm. Among them, three are graded crushed stone interlayer structures, and one is a semi-rigid base structure. The uneven settlement deformation of soft soil foundation is adjusted by setting a graded crushed interlayer. This inverted structure with a soft upper layer and rigid lower layer makes it easy to obtain higher compactness due to the large rigidity of the underlying layer. At the same time, the underlying layer with higher rigidity is conducive to the full play of the nonlinearity of graded crushed stone, to achieve the goal of homogenizing the uneven deformation of soft foundation. The four pavement structure parameters are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. (a) Calculation parameters of pavement structures.

Position	Material	Type I			Type II			
		Thickness (cm)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio	Material	Thickness (cm)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio
Surface course	SMA13	4	1, 400	0.35	SMA13	4	1, 400	0.35
	AC20-I	6	1, 200	0.30	AC20-I	6	1, 200	0.30
					ATB	12	1, 000	0.30
Roadbase	ATB	24	1, 000	0.30	CTB	20	1, 500	0.25
	GM	15	500	0.35	GM	16	500	0.35
Subbase	CTB	20	1, 500	0.25	CTB	20	1, 500	0.25

Table 1. (b) Calculation parameters of pavement structures.

Position	Type III				Type IV			
	Material	Thickness (cm)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio	Material	Thickness (cm)	Elastic modulus (MPa)	Poisson's ratio
Surface course	SMA13	4	1,400	0.35	SMA13	4	1,400	0.35
	AC20-I	6	1,200	0.30	AC20-I	6	1,200	0.30
	AC25-I	8	1,100	0.25				
Roadbase	CTB	40	1,500	0.25	ATB	28	1,000	0.30
					GM	20	500	0.35
Subbase	LFS	20	600	0.25	CTB	20	1,500	0.25

3.3. Model parameters of soft soil foundation

In the FEM simulation, different constitutive models are adopted for different materials to reflect the stress-strain relationship of different materials. The SMA and asphalt concrete have nonlinear characteristics, but compared with gravel base and soil foundation, the nonlinear characteristics of SMA and asphalt concrete are not obvious. Therefore, except for the consideration of the nonlinearity of graded crushed stone, the accuracy of calculation results will not be affected if the elastic model is adopted for other pavement structure layers [15]. A linear elastic model is adopted for the sand cushion, with an elastic modulus of 50 MPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.3, γ_d is $20 \text{ KN} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$, and the permeability coefficient is 1.0 m/d.

Because the soft soil is highly nonlinear, the error of the linear elastic model is large. The Drucker-Prager (D-P) ideal elastic-plastic constitutive model is adopted for embankment fill and muddy clay. The permeability coefficient of muddy clay is 0.00012 m/d. The model parameters can be seen in Tables 2 and 3. The modified clay plasticity is used to simulate the underlying silty clay, with the permeability coefficient of 0.00006 m/d, as seen in Table 4.

Table 2. Parameters of Drucker-Prager model.

Material	γ_d /($\text{KN} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$)	Cohesion c /KPa	Internal friction angle ϕ ($^\circ$)	Elastic modulus E /KPa	Poisson's ratio ν	β	k	ψ
Embankment (Hard clay)	18.3	29.3	36.5	20,000	0.4	28.7	1.00	28.7
Muddy clay	17.6	8.0	24.0	2,500	0.35	35.3	1.00	35.3

Table 3. Hardening parameters of the Drucker-Prager model.

Embankment (Hard clay)		Muddy clay	
$(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)/\text{KPa}$	ε^p	$(\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)/\text{KPa}$	ε^p
170.1	0.000	57.04	0.000
649.9	0.035	102.359	0.0082
740.3	0.050	177.59	0.024
801.4	0.073	282.18	0.056
840.8	0.091		

Table 4. Parameters of clay plasticity model.

Material	γ_d /($\text{KN} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$)	c /KPa	ϕ ($^\circ$)	κ	μ	λ	M	α_0	β	K	Void ratio e_1
Silty clay	17.8	22.4	31.6	0.02	0.31	0.07	1.27	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.02

3.4. Loading duration

Due to the weak permeability of soft soil foundation, its deformation process will go through a quite long period of time under the effect of additional stress generated by embankment, pavement structure, and vehicle load. This paper simulates the settlement in 15 years from the beginning of embankment filling to the completion of the project. In the calculation, the time step is used to control the graded loading, subbase, base, and pavement loading of the embankment (Figure 2). The embankment is divided into four layers for incremental analysis, and the thickness of each layer is 1.0 m. The simulation of the whole embankment construction process is simplified into the following steps: the interval after the first layer is filled is 30 days, the entire embankment filling period is 240 days, and the preloading period after the completion of embankment filling is 90 days.

Figure 2. History of loading case.

4. Mechanical response analysis of pavement structure

4.1. Settlement of embankment 15 years after completion

The displacement cloud chart, 15 years after the completion of the pavement, is obtained through numerical simulation. Taking Type I as an example, the settlement cloud chart 15 years after the completion is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Cloud chart of settlement 15 years after pavement completion (Type I).

The settlement of soft soil foundation consists of the primary consolidation settlement caused by the dissipation of pore water pressure and the secondary consolidation settlement caused by the creep

of the soil skeleton. The settlement history curves of four pavement structures over 15 years are shown in Figure 4. The curve relationship shows that the settlement is relatively fast in the first five years after completion, and 80% of the settlement has been completed, especially the settlement in the first year accounts for 1/3 of the total settlement, and the settlement gradually slows down in the next ten years. The settlement rate decreases from 4.2 cm/year (Type I) in the initial stage to 0.3 cm/year in the 15th year. The maximum settlement occurs in the backfilled embankment layer. There is little difference in the settlement of structure Types II, III, and IV within 15 years after completion, and the curves almost coincide. The settlement of Structure I is smaller than that of II, III, and IV. The analysis shows that the later settlement is smaller because the pavement of this structure is 69 cm, the pavement thickness of the last three structures is 78 cm, and the dead weight load of Structure I is smaller.

Figure 4. The historical curve of settlement during 15 years for four pavement structures.

The change law of the lateral settlement of the four pavement structures is the same. The settlement at the midpoint of the road surface is the largest, and the settlement at both endpoints is the smallest. The settlement line is a curved basin after completion. The post-construction settlement of the road surface midpoint of the four structures is 12.49, 15.72, 16.01, and 16.10 cm, respectively (Figure 5). Except for Structure I, the post-construction settlement of Structure II is the smallest, because the pavement structural materials of Structure II have greater stiffness and greater load expansion capacity, resulting in smaller settlement. The predicted post-construction settlement of the four pavement structures is less than 30 cm. The calculation also shows that the settlement of Types I and IV is 14.2 cm and 18.5 cm, respectively, in the 30th year, and the secondary consolidation contribution accounts for 15-20%.

Figure 5. 15 years post-settlement of four pavement structures.

The settlement of soft soil subgrade is large, and it takes a long time to complete the consolidation settlement. Due to the trapezoidal distribution of the embankment load, when the embankment load and the vehicle load are applied on the soft foundation, the soil produces uneven vertical deformation. The engineers proposed two settlement curves of the embankment surface (Figure 6). One is in the form of a quadratic parabola:

$$y = \frac{4\delta}{(2L)^2}x^2 - \delta \tag{4}$$

Another distribution according to the cosine function is:

$$y = -\delta\cos(\pi x/2L) \tag{5}$$

where δ is the maximum differential settlement between the middle and endpoint of embankment, L is half the width of the embankment top surface, x is the horizontal distance from the center point of the embankment, and y is the difference between any point in the curve and the top surface of the embankment.

Figure 6. Calculation model of embankment settlement.

Figure 7. Embankment settlement curve of Structure A.

Comparing the results obtained from Equation (4) and Equation (5) with the simulation value, the settlement curve is consistent (see Figure 7), and the calculation value of Equation (4) is closer to the simulation.

4.2. Differential settlement analysis

The uneven settlement of pavement structure is the most noticeable problem during the construction of soft soil pavement. The uneven lateral settlement of the road surface will cause the maximum settlement at the midpoint of the road surface, which will lead to a smaller cross slope, and the lateral drainage of the pavement will become very difficult. At the same time, uneven settlement causes additional stress on the pavement. If the sum of such additional stress and load stress exceeds the tensile stress at the bottom of the base course, the early damage of asphalt pavement will be accelerated.

The differential settlement curves of the four structures are shown in Figure 8. It can be seen from Figure 8 that the differential settlements of the four structures are 1.40 cm, 1.92 cm, 1.98 cm, and 2.03

cm, respectively. The differential settlements of Structure I are the smallest, while the other three structures are close, Structure IV is the largest, and Structures II and III are in the middle. The thickness of the graded crushed stone layer in Structure IV is 20 cm, and the nonlinearity of the graded crushed stone cannot be fully exerted, which reduces the overall stiffness of the pavement structure, resulting in a decrease in the load diffusion capacity and a large uneven settlement. This also shows from another aspect that although the graded gravel layer has good coordination, the thickness should not be too thick to avoid an increase in uneven settlement. The thickness of a properly graded gravel layer should be controlled within 12~18 cm.

Figure 8. Post-differential settlements of four pavement structures.

4.3. Relationship between differential settlement and modulus of subbase

Figure 9 shows the relationship between differential settlement of embankment and modulus of subbase for four pavement structures. The data shows that for different pavement structures, the differential settlement changes little with the increase of the modulus of subbase.

Figure 9. Relationships between differential embankment settlements and subbase modulus.

5. Foundation reinforcement

To reduce the total settlement and differential settlement of soft soil foundation, various reinforcement structures are often used to form a composite foundation. According to the direction of reinforcement in

the foundation, it can be divided into horizontal reinforcement (reinforcement material) and vertical reinforcement (pile) composite foundation. In this paper, geogrid and CFG pile are considered, respectively, to analyze the displacement and deformation characteristics of the subgrade.

5.1. Geogrid reinforcement

The geogrid of one layer is laid under the embankment, and its sectional area is 0.00015 m². The tensile modulus is 3.87×10⁴ MPa/m, and Poisson’s ratio is 0.25.

After the geogrid is laid for reinforcement, the settlement in 15 years after completion has little impact, and the uneven settlement is still 1.4 cm. At the bottom of the grid, the settlement is only reduced by about 0.04 cm (Figure 10). This shows that it is not feasible to use a geogrid to reduce the uneven settlement of soft soil foundations.

Figure 10. (a) Settlement of pavement surface.

Figure 10. (b) Settlement of the bottom surface of the geogrid.

5.2. Geogrid and pile foundation reinforcement

The geogrid is laid under the embankment, and CFG piles (cement flyash gravel pile) are put in the muddy clay layer under the sand cushion. The pile diameter is 0.5 m, the length is 11.5 m, the pile spacing is 1.0 m, and there are 27 CFG piles (Figure 11). The elastic modulus of the pile is 120 MPa, Poisson’s ratio is 0.20, and the permeability coefficient is 1.0×10⁻⁶ m/d.

Figure 11. Geogrid and pile reinforced soft foundation model.

According to the calculation results, after the pile group is added, the settlement after 15 years of completion is significantly reduced, the settlement of the middle point of the road surface is reduced from 12.49 cm to 1.4 cm, and the uneven settlement is reduced from 1.4 cm to 0.13 cm. The settlement of the bottom of the grid is reduced from 28.67 cm to 5.34 cm, with the maximum reduction of 23.33 cm. The uneven settlement value decreased from 22.07 cm to 3.3 cm, and the settlement decreased significantly (Figure 12).

Figure 12. (a) Settlement of pavement surface (geogrid+pile).

Figure 12. (b) Settlement of the bottom surface of the geogrid (geogrid+pile).

According to the settlement observation data of a soft soil section, the measured pavement settlement value in the fifth year after the reinforcement of geogrid+cfg pile is 1.3 cm (simulated 1.2 cm, error is 7.7%), and the simulation result is close to the measured value.

5.3. Sensitivity analysis

5.3.1. Influence of CFG pile length. The analysis shows that there is a significant negative correlation between pile length and settlement ($R^2=0.94$). The pile length increased from 8 m to 15 m, and the settlement decreased from 9.8 cm to 1.4 cm, a decrease of 85.7%. The settlement decreases by about 5.2% with the increase of pile length by 1 m. When the pile length >12 m, the settlement attenuation rate slows down (from 0.6 cm/m to 0.2 cm/m).

5.3.2. Influence of pavement thickness. When the pavement thickness >75 cm, the self-weight load becomes the main controlling factor of settlement. Too thick pavement will aggravate self-weight settlement. It is recommended to optimize the thickness to about 70 cm.

5.3.3. Influence of elastic modulus of base course. When the elastic modulus increases from 500 MPa to 2,000 MPa, the settlement decreases from 15.1 cm to 14.3 cm (a decrease of 5.3%). Therefore, the settlement of soft foundation mainly comes from soil consolidation, and the improvement of base stiffness has limited influence on the stress distribution of deep soil.

5.3.4. Influence of geogrid spacing. The geogrid spacing increased from 0.5 m to 2.0 m, the differential settlement increased from 1.35 cm to 1.48 cm (an increase of 9.6%), and the settlement at the center of the road surface was almost unchanged (± 0.2 cm). When the spacing is more than 1.5 m, the change rate of differential settlement is less than 3%, and the effect of grid reinforcement is significantly weakened. The grid should be used to assist in controlling local deformation, and the recommended spacing is ≤ 1.5 m to play a role in coordinating deformation.

The parameter sensitivity analysis shows that the important parameters affecting the settlement value are pile length, pavement thickness, base modulus, and grid spacing, and the CFG pile length is the core parameter of settlement control.

5.4. Cost-benefit comparison

According to the actual engineering analysis, the long-term cost-benefit comparison of different reinforcement schemes is shown in Table 5.

Table 5. Cost-benefit analysis of three schemes.

Reinforcement scheme	Initial cost (RMB yuan/m ²)	50-year maintenance cost (RMB yuan/m ²)	Total cost (RMB yuan/m ²)	Settlement value in the 15th year (cm)	Total settlement reduction (%)
Geogrid	120	180	300	11.09	5-8
CFG pile	380	50	430	1.92	80-85
Geogrid & CFG pile	300	30	330	1.27	90-95

It can be seen from Table 5 that, compared with the geogrid reinforcement scheme, the total cost of the geogrid+cfg pile combination scheme increases little, while the settlement is significantly less. By comprehensive cost-benefit comparison, the geogrid+cfg pile combination scheme is the best.

6. Conclusion

The adaptability of four different pavement structures to soft foundation settlement is simulated by the finite element method, and the influence of changing the elastic modulus of subbase on the settlement value is analyzed. To reduce the settlement of pavement, a treatment scheme by geogrid and pile foundation is proposed, and the settlement characteristics of pavement after soft soil foundation reinforcement are studied.

(1) The long-term settlement of different pavement structures is close. The settlement of subgrade increases with the increase of fill, and the initial settlement rate is greater than the later settlement rate. The settlement of the embankment is in the shape of a curved basin, that is, in the direction of the cross section of the embankment, the midpoint settlement of the embankment is large, while the endpoint sides are small. 15 years after the completion of pavement structure type I, the differential settlement is 1.4 cm.

(2) Increasing the elastic modulus of the subbase has little influence on the settlement. If the thickness of the base course is increased, the settlement of the pavement will increase to a certain extent due to the increase in the dead load. Therefore, the thickness of the base course should be controlled within a reasonable range.

(3) The graded crushed stone has good coordination, but the thickness should not be too thick to avoid an increase in uneven settlement. The thickness of a properly graded gravel layer should be controlled within 12~18 cm.

(4) As a flexible material, the shear strength of geogrid is small, and its influence on differential settlement in a large range is limited. It is not feasible to use a geogrid to reduce the uneven settlement of soft soil foundations. After the pile composite foundation is adopted, the overall stiffness of the soft soil foundation has been effectively enhanced. After 15 years, the settlement has decreased significantly, and the uneven settlement is very small.

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